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D 4.3 Guidance, tools & materials for Digital Responsibility

A repository supporting the creation
of responsible digital technology

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents guidance, tools and materials in a clear structure based on the Digital Responsibility Goals. As a repository it offers a multidisciplinary guide to Digital Responsibility, combining insights from IT, public policy, social sciences, and law, and features ethical principles, best practices, and tools essential for responsible digital technology. Ultimately meant to be transferred to a wiki structure, it aims for continuous evolution, enhancing flexibility, and fostering synergies with other DRG4FOOD project deliverables, like the open-source toolbox. In the end, a blueprint for a Digital Responsibility Report is discussed.

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1 Introduction

In a world where our lives are increasingly intertwined with technology, the urgency to create digital technology that is ethical, inclusive, and responsible has become a central concern. Hence, this document emerges as a foundational resource for DRG4FOOD's mission to offer an answer to this concern, bringing together guidance, materials, and tools designed to support participants of the project in their journey towards more responsible technological innovation.

Digital technology is not just a tool; it's a significant part of how we live, communicate, learn, and solve problems. Despite this centrality in our lives digital technologies are often not designed with us humans in mind. This document shall serve as a compass, providing insights and directions that encourage developers of digital technology to make informed choices and foster the development of technology that respects human values, promotes equity, and mitigates harm. As such, the document is structured around the Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs) framework that constitutes the ideational underpinning of DRG4FOOD's mission to foster a trustworthy data-driven food system.

The seven DRGs are guiding principles for a digital ecosystem that prioritises human identity, social cohesion and trust. They were developed in a multistakeholder approach with experts from various fields. Designed to reduce complexity in our increasingly digitised lives they can make responsible behaviour in the digital world visible, comparable, and comprehensible.

Similar to how the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) enable a common agenda for a more sustainable planet, the DRGs seek to promote digital technologies embedded in universal rights and values. By utilising the DRGs and their guiding criteria as ideological pillars in the conception, development and operation of digital services, trustworthiness "by design" is promoted.

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This document addresses each DRG as a separated dimension of Digital Responsibility and provides diverse resources, explaining their relevance, drawing from various fields, such as information technology, public policy, social sciences or law. The integration of different disciplines aims to provide a well-rounded understanding and create comprehensive strategies for developing and using digital technology responsibly.

The repository is structured to offer a clear and comprehensive repository, outlining ethical principles, best practices, and practical tools essential for building responsible digital technology. It includes resources such as comprehensible governmental guidelines, industry best practices, standards, research findings, and tools for evaluation, providing a diverse and integrated view.

Additionally, this repository is meant to be a living document, evolving to accommodate changes in the technological landscape and to incorporate new insights and perspectives throughout the DRG4FOOD project. That is why this specific document can only be a starting point. For i) more flexibility on its contents and ii) to increase the ease-of-use for DRG4FOOD participants, this repository will also be transposed into an online searchable “wiki” structure – as part of the overall toolbox - that can be amended and is of better use to practitioners in the digital world.

Further, this transferral into a wiki structure opens opportunities to enable synergies with other Deliverables of the DRG4FOOD project, such as the open-source toolbox with enablers (i.e. D5.1 Virtual food system enablers and their demonstrations).

How to use this document?

The following pages lay out a collection of resources that can support developers and providers of digital technology in complying with the DRG framework mentioned above and therefore promote a more human-centered digital ecosystem.

The information is structured to show i) a guiding criterion that a resource is connected to ii) a short description of the resource iii) a URL to the resource iv) tags for the context of use and v) a comment on the relevance and potential use of the resource.

Developers and providers of digital technology in the context of DRG4FOOD may consult this repository to support their compliance with requirements regarding the DRG framework (or use the wiki connected to this document).

2 Guidance, tools and materials

In the following the resources will be categorized by the DRG they are supporting. At the beginning of each section an overview of the goal and related guiding criteria will be given, followed by a list of resources, which guiding criteria they are catering to and what their relevance is to the broader field of responsible digital technology.

1. DRG#1 Digital Literacy

1.1. Description

Digital Literacy and **unrestricted** as well as **competent access** to digital services and infrastructure are prerequisites for the **sovereign** and **self-determined** use of digital technologies.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#1.1 Information offered for digital products, services, and processes must be designed individually and in a way that is suitable for the target group.
DRG#1.2 Access to digital products, services, and processes must be reliable and barrier-free.
DRG#1.3 Acceptance of digital products, services, and processes must be proactively considered in design and operation. This includes measures on equity, diversity & inclusion.
DRG#1.4 Education on the opportunities and risks of the digital transformation is essential - everyone is entitled to education on digital matters.
DRG#1.5 Awareness for related topics such as sustainability, climate protection, and diversity/inclusion (e.g., along UN SDGs) should be raised, where applicable.

1.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
1.1	Simple language generator	Rewordify	tool; user-friendliness; privacy;	Language used for explaining functionalities or legal notices to the user should be, as much as possible, free of jargon and easily understandable. This tool simplifies difficult words and phrases.
1.2	Web Content	WCAG	guidelines; accessibility;	A set of guidelines created by the World Wide Web Consortium

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	Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)			(W3C) to help make web content more accessible to people with disabilities. The guidelines cover a wide range of disabilities, including visual, hearing, and mobility impairments, as well as cognitive and language-related disabilities. The latest version of the guidelines is WCAG 2.1, and it covers four main principles: perceivability, operability, understandability, and robustness (POUR).
1.2	Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool (WAVE)	WAVE	tool; accessibility; website;	WAVE is a tool that automatically evaluates the accessibility of web pages, highlighting areas that pass or fail accessibility standards.
1.2	Web Accessibility Principles (WAI)	WAI	guidelines; materials; accessibility;	The Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) is a project by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) that aims to promote and develop guidelines, techniques, and resources to ensure that the web is accessible to people with disabilities. The WAI's guidelines are organized into different levels to help web developers, designers, and content creators understand and implement accessibility features effectively
1.3	User Experience Design Checklists	UX Design Checklists	guidelines; checklist; UX; user-friendliness;	UX design is important for Digital Responsibility because it determines how easy or difficult it is for users to navigate a digital product and accomplish their goals. A good UX design makes it easy for users to understand and use a digital product, while a bad UX design can lead to frustration and even exclusion.
1.5	Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	SDGs	materials; sustainability;	The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) need to be accounted for when developing digital technologies to ensure that technological advancements are equitable, inclusive, environmentally sustainable, and conducive to addressing global challenges.

2. DRG#2 Cybersecurity

2.1. Description

Cybersecurity protects systems against **compromise and manipulation** by unauthorized actors and ensures the **protection of users and their data** - from data collection to data utilization. It is a basic prerequisite for the **responsible operation of digital solutions**.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#2.1 Developers and providers of digital products, services and processes assume responsibility for cybersecurity. Users also bear a part of the responsibility.
DRG#2.2 Developers and providers of digital technology are responsible for appropriate security measures and constantly develop them further. Digital technologies are designed to be resistant to compromise.
DRG#2.3 A holistic view and appropriate implementation of cybersecurity are considered along the lifecycle, value chain, and the entire solution.
DRG#2.4 Developers and providers of digital products, services, and processes must account for how they provide security for users and their data - while maintaining trade secrets.
DRG#2.5 Business, politics, authorities, civil society and science must collaboratively shape the objectives and measures of cybersecurity. This requires open and transparent cooperation and disclosures.

2.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
2.2	Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)	CWE Top 25	materials; vulnerabilities; cybersecurity;	There are some well-known vulnerabilities that every developer should be aware of and should fortify against. Most of the answer options are taken from the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) which is a community-developed list of common software and hardware weakness types that have security

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				ramifications. By following the CWE Top 25, developers are able to significantly reduce the number of weaknesses that occur in their software.
2.2	OWASP Application Security Verification Standard (ASVS)	ASVS	guidelines; checklist; certification; cybersecurity;	The OWASP Application Security Verification Standard (ASVS) can be used to create responsible technology by providing a framework for establishing secure application development practices, thus ensuring that technology is built with robust security controls to protect user data and privacy, and to prevent malicious exploits, thereby contributing to trust and reliability in the digital ecosystem
2.2	Secure development and deployment guidance (UK National Cyber Security Center)	UK NCSC principles	guidelines; best practice; cybersecurity;	The UK Secure Development and Deployment Guidance can be used to create responsible technology by offering a comprehensive set of guidelines and best practices for developing and deploying secure, privacy-respecting, and resilient digital solutions, thereby fostering a safer and more trustworthy digital environment
2.2	BSA Framework for Secure Software – A new approach to securing the software lifecycle (BSA - The Software Alliance)	BSA Framework for Secure Software	guidelines; best practice; standards; SDL; cybersecurity;	The BSA framework for secure software can be used to create responsible technology by providing organizations with a set of best practices, guidelines, and principles to integrate security into

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				the software development lifecycle, thereby ensuring the development of secure, resilient, and trustworthy digital solutions that safeguard user privacy and data.
2.2	Cyber Essentials readiness toolkit	NCSC Cyber Essentials (Plus)	tool; guidelines; certification; best practice; standards; cybersecurity;	UK Cyber Essentials offers a self-assessment, outlining a clear set of basic controls and guidelines to protect against common cyber threats, thereby ensuring the development, implementation, and maintenance of secure and reliable digital services and products that prioritize user safety and data protection. They offer a cybersecurity certification under "Cyber Essentials Plus".
2.2;2.3	Global Cybersecurity Alliance Toolkit	GCA Toolkit	Guidelines; tools;	The GCA Cybersecurity Toolkits provides free and effective tools that individuals and organizations of any size can use right now to take action to reduce cyber risk.
2.3; 6.1;	Recommendations for publishing End-of-life dates and support timelines	EOL/EOS guidance	guidelines; user-friendliness; SDL; transparency;	When software reaches its end-of-life, users should be encouraged to migrate to newer versions of the software, switch to alternative software solutions, or make other arrangements to ensure their systems remain secure and functional. It's important for users to be aware of the lifecycle of the software they rely on to make informed decisions and

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				avoid potential risks associated with using unsupported or outdated software.
2.2	Advancing Software Security in the EU - ENISA	Advancing Software Security in the EU - ENISA	materials; standards; certification; cybersecurity;	A study discussing key elements of software security and providing a concise overview of the most relevant existing approaches and standards while identifying shortcomings associated with the secure software development landscape, related to different inherent aspects of the process. Further, it provides an overview over the newly established EU cybersecurity certification framework and the EU cybersecurity certification schemes.
2.5; 6.2;	CERT disclosure policy templates	CERT templates	materials; templates; vulnerability; transparency;	“Sharing is caring” - a vulnerability disclosure policy is essential from a user and ecosystem perspective as it provides a structured and secure way for security researchers to report vulnerabilities. This approach helps in identifying and fixing potential threats before they can be exploited by malicious actors, safeguarding user data, maintaining system integrity, and contributing to an overall safer digital environment. A bug bounty program can serve as an effective incentive for security

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				researchers to actively look for vulnerabilities.
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3. DRG#3 Privacy

3.1. Description

Protection of privacy - with consistent **purpose limitation and data minimisation** - allows users to act **confidently** in the digital world. **Privacy by design and default** enable responsible data usage. **Users are given control and providers must account** for how they protect privacy.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#3.1 Developers and providers of digital products, services, and processes must take responsibility for protecting the privacy of their users.
DRG#3.2 When dealing with personal data basic principles of data protection are respected, in particular strict purpose limitations and data minimisation.
DRG#3.3 Privacy protection is considered throughout the entire lifecycle and should be considered a default setting.
DRG#3.4 Users have control over their personal data and their use - including the rights to access, rectify, object, erase, data portability, restrict processing and avoid automated decision-making.
DRG#3.5 Providers must account for how they protect users' privacy and personal data - while maintaining necessary trade secrets.

3.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
3.1	GDPR checklist for data controllers	GDPR checklist	guidelines; checklist; privacy; GDPR;	Comprehensive compliance with the GDPR promotes trust in digital technology by ensuring that users' personal data is handled with transparency, integrity, and confidentiality, fostering a sense of security and control among individuals.

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3.1	Data Protection Impact Assessment	Data Protection Impact Assessment (+ Template)	tool; template; privacy; GDPR;	Conducting a (voluntary) GDPR Data Protection Impact Assessment helps developers identify and mitigate risks associated with data processing, thereby enhancing data protection, building consumer trust.
3.1	Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) Software	CNIL - Open-source PIA software	tool; software; privacy; GDPR;	
3.2; 6.1;	How can I demonstrate that my organisation is compliant with the GDPR?	GDPR compliance demonstration	materials; privacy; certification; GPDR;	Demonstrating GDPR compliance fosters trust with customers and stakeholders, ensuring data privacy and meeting regulatory requirements.
3.2; 6.1;	GDPR compliance self-assessment	GDPR self-assessment	tool; GDPR;	In the EU data protection principles are enshrined in the GDPR but active demonstration of compliance signals trustworthiness and Digital Responsibility.
3.3	Guidance on Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PET)	Guidance on Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PET)	materials; privacy;	Privacy Enhancing Technologies, are advanced tools, applications, or methods that protect users' privacy by minimizing personal data, obscuring data, or enabling individuals to control their own data, thereby enhancing confidentiality and preventing unauthorized access and data breaches.
3.4	Privacy is an afterthought in the software lifecycle. That needs to change	Stackoverflow	materials; privacy; SDL;	The key to combining privacy and innovation, rather than pitting them against one another, is baking privacy into the software development lifecycle. Analogous to application security's upstream shift into the development cycle, privacy

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				belongs at the outset of development
3.5	How to write a user-friendly GDPR-compliant privacy notice	GDPR privacy notice best practices (+ template)	guidelines; privacy; best practice; user-friendliness; template;	Privacy policies detailing data collection purposes are often obfuscated or misleadingly presented. They need to be understandable in a way that users are completely aware of what they are agreeing to.
3.5; 1.3;	Workshop Kit - Thinking the GDPR in the user experience	CNIL - Workshop Kit	GDPR; privacy; UX;	Privacy considerations in UX choices are essential because the user experience should prioritize and reflect a user's right to data protection and confidentiality, ensuring that interactions are both intuitive and respectful of personal information.

4. DRG#4 Data Fairness

4.1. Description

Non-personal data must also be **protected and handled** according to its value. At the same time, suitable mechanisms must be defined to make **data transferable and applicable between parties**. This is the only way to ensure **balanced cooperation** between different stakeholders in **data ecosystems**.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#4.1 When collecting or re-using data, proactive care is taken to ensure the integrity of the data, considering whether any gaps, inaccuracies or bias might exist.
DRG#4.2 In digital ecosystems the exchange of data between all parties must be clearly described and regulated. The goal must be fair participation in the benefits achieved through the exchange of data.
DRG#4.3 Developers and providers of digital technologies must clearly define and communicate the purpose with which they use and process data (including non-personal data).
DRG#4.4 When providing or creating datasets the “FAIR” data principles are satisfied, especially in cases where re-use would benefit society as a whole. "FAIR" stands for Findable, Accessible, Inter-operable, Reusable.
DRG#4.5 Users providing or creating data must be equipped with mechanisms to control and withdraw their data - they shall have a say regarding data usage policies.

4.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
4.1; 6.1;	Datasetcard creation tool	Create a dataset card	tool; dataset; bias; transparency;	Dataset cards / datasheets can be used to support responsible technology by providing comprehensive metadata and context about a dataset, including its origin, composition, intended use, and limitations. This transparency helps
4.1; 6.1;	Purposeful and Transparent Dataset Documentation for Responsible AI	Data Cards	materials; dataset; bias; transparency;	

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4.3; 6.1;	Datasheets for datasets	Datasheets for datasets	guidelines; dataset; bias; transparency;	developers, researchers, and users understand potential biases, ethical considerations, and the appropriate use of the dataset, thereby promoting fairness, accountability, and trustworthiness in data-driven technologies and applications.
4.2	Open Data Handbook	Open Data Handbook	guidelines; dataset; license; open data;	Open data contributes to responsible technology by fostering transparency, accountability, and inclusivity, enabling a diverse range of stakeholders to scrutinize, innovate, and build upon available datasets, thereby creating applications and solutions that address societal needs, mitigate biases, uphold ethical standards, and ensure the equitable distribution of technology benefits
4.3; 6.4;	How to write a good open data policy	ODI	guidelines; dataset; open data; transparency;	A data policy (supplementary to a privacy policy) ensures comprehensive transparency over all types of data, addressing not only user privacy but also data utilisation, sharing, security, and lifecycle management, thereby fostering trust.
4.4	FAIR data principles	FAIR	guidelines; checklist; open data;	By adhering to the FAIR principles, (i) researchers and organizations can share and integrate data more effectively, (ii) data can be easily located through search engines and data repositories, (iii) interoperability and reusability enable data from different disciplines to be combined, fostering interdisciplinary research, (iv) proper documentation

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				and persistent identifiers improve data preservation efforts, (v) well-described metadata and clear identifiers enhance the credibility of data, (vi) responsible data sharing and accountability in research is emphasized, (vii) accessible and reusable data can lead to more impactful research outcomes.
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5. DRG#5 Trustworthy Algorithms

5.1. Description

Once data has been collected, it must be **processed with the aim of trustworthiness**. This is true for **simple algorithms** as well as for more **complex systems** up to **autonomously acting systems**.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#5.1 Algorithms, their application, and the datasets they are used or trained on are designed to provide a maximum of fairness and inclusion.
DRG#5.2 The individual and overall societal impact of algorithms is regularly reviewed and the review documented. Depending on the results, proportional corrective measures must be taken.
DRG#5.3 Outputs of algorithmic processing are comprehensible and explainable. Where possible outputs should be reproducible.
DRG#5.4 AI systems must be robust and designed to withstand subtle attempts to manipulate data or algorithms.
DRG#5.5 AI systems must be designed and implemented in such a way that independent control of their mode of action is possible.

5.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
5.1	IEEE Standard Model Process for Addressing Ethical Concerns during System Design	IEEE	guidelines; standards; SDL;	A set of processes by which organizations can include consideration of ethical values throughout the stages of concept exploration and development is established by this standard. Management and engineering in transparent communication with selected stakeholders for ethical values elicitation and prioritization is supported by this standard, involving

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				traceability of ethical values through an operational concept, value propositions, and value dispositions in the system design.
5.1	EU Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI	EU Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI	guidelines; checklist; AI;	The Guidelines put forward a set of 7 key requirements that AI systems should meet in order to be deemed trustworthy. A specific assessment list aims to help verify the application of each of the key requirements.
5.2	Algorithmic Impact Assessment	US CIO	tool; bias;	Algorithmic Impact Assessments (AIAs) are crucial to responsible technology as they help identify and evaluate the potential social, ethical, and environmental impacts of algorithms, facilitating transparency, accountability, and fairness, and ensuring that the deployment of such technologies aligns with societal values, mitigates biases and inequalities, and safeguards the rights and well-being of individuals and communities.
5.3; 6.1;	What is Explainable AI (XAI)?	XAI	materials; AI; user-friendliness; transparency;	Explainable AI refers to methods to design artificial intelligence systems to be transparent and understandable by human users. The goal of XAI is to create AI models that can clearly articulate their decision-making processes, enabling users, developers, and stakeholders to interpret and trust the AI's outputs and actions. Explainability in AI is crucial for understanding and addressing potential biases, ensuring fairness, building user trust, fostering accountability, and complying with regulations

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				that require transparency in automated decision-making.
5.4	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)	ALTAI	tool; checklist; bias; AI;	The ALTAI (Algorithmic Accountability and Transparency Assessment Tool) self-assessment is a tool developed by the European Union to help organizations evaluate the transparency and accountability of their algorithmic systems. It aims to ensure that algorithms are designed and implemented responsibly, considering aspects such as fairness, explainability, data protection, and overall impact on individuals and society. By using the ALTAI self-assessment, organizations can identify areas of improvement, mitigate risks, and enhance the trustworthiness and ethical considerations of their algorithmic applications.
5.5; 6.1;	Model Cards for Model Reporting	Model Cards for Model Reporting	materials; best practice; transparency;	Model Cards can be used to establish transparency about algorithmic systems by providing detailed documentation and transparency about a machine learning model's purpose, performance, datasets, limitations, and ethical considerations, thereby enabling developers, users, and stakeholders to understand the model's behavior and potential biases, make informed decisions, ensure fairness, and hold developers accountable for the impacts of the technology.
5.5; 6.1;	Model Card Creator Tool	Model Card Creator Tool	tool; transparency;	

6. DRG#6 Transparency

6.1. Description

Proactive **transparency for users and all other stakeholders** is needed. This includes transparency of the **principles that underlie digital products, services, and processes**, and transparency of the **digital solution and its components**.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#6.1 Organisations establish transparency - about digital products, services, and processes as well as the organisation, business models, data flows, and technologies employed.
DRG#6.2 Transparency is implemented through interactive communication (for example, between providers and users), and mechanisms for interaction are actively offered.
DRG#6.3 The application of digital technology is made transparent wherever there is an interaction between people and the digital technology (for example, the use of chatbots).
DRG#6.4 In addition to transparency for users, transparency should also be provided for other stakeholders (e.g., businesses, science, governments) – while maintaining trade secrets.
DRG#6.5 Organisations must outline how they will make transparency verifiable and thus hold themselves accountable for their actions in the digital space.

6.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
6.1; 4.1	Datasetcard creation tool	Create a dataset card	tool; dataset; bias; transparency;	Dataset cards / datasheets can be used to support responsible technology by providing comprehensive metadata and context about a dataset, including its origin, composition, intended use, and limitations. This transparency helps developers, researchers, and users understand potential biases, ethical considerations, and the appropriate use of the dataset, thereby

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				promoting fairness, accountability, and trustworthiness in data-driven technologies and applications.
6.1; 5.5	Model Card Creator Tool	Model Card Creator Tool	tool; transparency;	Model Cards can be used to establish transparency about algorithmic systems by providing detailed documentation and transparency about a machine learning model's purpose, performance, datasets, limitations, and ethical considerations, thereby enabling developers, users, and stakeholders to understand the model's behavior and potential biases, make informed decisions, ensure fairness, and hold developers accountable for the impacts of the technology.
6.4; 4.3	How to write a good open data policy	ODI	guidelines; dataset; open data; transparency;	A data policy (supplementary to a privacy policy) ensures comprehensive transparency over all types of data, addressing not only user privacy but also data utilisation, sharing, security, and lifecycle management, thereby fostering trust.
6.5; 2.4	ENISA Cybersecurity Certification	ENISA	materials; certification; cybersecurity; transparency;	Certification for digital technologies supports transparency and trust by validating that specific standards, guidelines, and regulations are met, thereby assuring users and stakeholders of the credibility, safety, and reliability of the technology.
6.5; 3.4	GDPR Certification	Europrivacy certification	materials; certification; cybersecurity; transparency;	

7. DRG#7 Human Agency & Identity

7.1. Description

Especially in the digital space, we must **protect our identity** and **preserve human responsibility**. Preserving the multifaceted human identity must be a prerequisite for any digital development. The resulting digital products, services, and processes are **human-centered, inclusive, ethically sensitive, and sustainable**, maintaining human agency at all times.

Guiding Criteria
DRG#7.1 The preservation of the multifaceted human identity must be the basis for any digital development. Resulting digital technologies are user centric, respect personal autonomy, dignity, and limit commodification.
DRG#7.2 Sustainability and climate protection must be part of design choices of digital technologies and digital business models and implemented in practice (especially in accordance with the UN SDGs).
DRG#7.3 Digital products, services, and processes promote responsible, non-manipulative communication. Where possible, communication takes place unfiltered.
DRG#7.4 Digital technology always remains under human conception and control - it can be reconfigured throughout its deployment.
DRG#7.5 Digital technology may only be applied to benefit individuals and humankind and promote the wellbeing of humanity.

7.2. Guidance, tools, materials

Guiding Criteria	Description	Resource	Tag	Relevance
7.1	Planning Human-Centered Design Process	UX/UI Bootcamp (article)	guidelines; user-friendliness; UX; UI;	Human-centered design in software development is an approach that prioritizes the needs, preferences, and contexts of the end-users at every stage of the design and development process, ensuring that the final product is accessible, user-friendly, and effective in

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				solving users' problems or fulfilling their needs.
7.2; 1.5	UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	UN Sustainable Development Goals	materials; sustainability;	The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) need to be accounted for when developing digital technologies to ensure that technological advancements are equitable, inclusive, environmentally sustainable, and conducive to addressing global challenges.
7.2	How to implement Green Coding	Green Software Foundation	guidelines; sustainability; SDL;	Green coding refers to the practice of writing software code in a way that minimizes the environmental impact by optimizing resource efficiency, reducing energy consumption, and decreasing carbon footprint, often through efficient algorithms, reducing redundancy, and utilizing less memory and computing power.
7.5	Code of Conduct	Hippocratic Oath for Technologists	materials; guidelines; template;	The "Hippocratic Oath for technologists" is an ethical guideline inspired by the medical Hippocratic Oath, encouraging technology professionals to work ethically and responsibly. It urges creators to consider the societal impacts of their developments and to prioritize the well-being of all individuals. The Oath seeks to foster a commitment to ethical practices and to avoid harm, pushing for responsible creation, development, and deployment of technology while considering its broader impacts on society and individuals.

3 Outlook: Annual Digital Responsibility Report

DRG4FOOD will publish an annual Digital Responsibility Report detailing how the project contributed to Digital Responsibility and the creation of responsible technology. As the first reporting period (Dec 2022 – Dec 2023) coincides with the laying of the groundwork for the implementation of DRG4FOOD's mission there will be a limited scope of activities to report on, also because reporting on open call participants will only be possible as soon as successful call participants take up their work in March 2024 (see D 6.1).

Hence, the first Digital Responsibility Report will focus its reporting on 1) project internal activities related to Digital Responsibility and 2) the development/selection of potential Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure Digital Responsibility in consecutive reports.

In the light of this, the prospective structure of the Digital Responsibility Report 2022/2023 will focus on the following:

- **Internal evaluation of Digital Responsibility:**
 - *How was Digital Responsibility implemented within the project? (Selection of digital tools; data management; coaching of consortium partners)*
 - *How did the DRG framework and DRG4FOOD's mission influence mindset & work of consortium partners? (Concise individual reports from consortium partners)*
- **Progress on deliverables enabling Digital Responsibility:**
 - *Which deliverables contributed in which way to strengthen Digital Responsibility? (Screening of Digital Responsibility related aspects from deliverables)*
- **Potential KPIs:**
 - *Following from the preceding evaluations: Which KPIs emerge for digitally responsible behaviour and which supplementary measurement criteria can still be envisioned? (Focus on setup for Digital Responsibility Report 2023/2024 and evaluation system for open call participants)*

Ultimately, the first report should provide a blueprint for a preliminary evaluation system that evaluates (software development) projects according to their strengths and weaknesses in developing responsible digital technology. This system will not only provide transparency about the progress and mission of DRG4FOOD but will also serve as orientation for open call participants detailing where there is still room for improvement in relation to Digital Responsibility (as of report 2023/2024).

At the end of the DRG4FOOD project the resulting evaluation and reporting system should be robust and applicable to use cases beyond DRG4FOOD, contributing a tool for fostering the broader ecosystem of responsible digital technologies (which means, once finalised, the reporting system itself should become part of the repository set out in this document and the

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overall DRG4FOOD toolbox). However, the potential re-usability of the Digital Responsibility reporting system goes beyond the toolbox, offering a standardised model for assessing Digital Responsibility across diverse sectors and platforms. By establishing a set of benchmarks and KPIs, organisations could adopt and adapt the system to evaluate their own digital initiatives, ensuring that they align with the principles of responsible technology. Such a reporting framework is the first step towards a harmonized approach to Digital Responsibility, allowing for more consistent evaluation and comparison across different entities.

Lastly, the system could contribute to a shared vision of ethical tech development in a global digital ecosystem. Organisations, regardless of their size or domain, could leverage this system to enhance their credibility, trustworthiness, and reputation, motivating them to invest further in responsible digital practices.

